

Productivity of online learning: Basis towards the enhancement of academic performance of School of Business and Computer Studies students in St. Dominic College of Asia

Jessa Gepiga*, Jonalyn H. Lacorte, Patricia Joy S. Martin, Jairah M. Pedraza, Merced Dianne B. Pineda, Kathleen Mae D. Rea, Pastor Judith Valcorza
Accountancy Department, School of Business and Computer Studies, St. Dominic College of Asia,
Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines
*Corresponding author

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to gather relevant information about students' performance during online classes. The researchers conducted a survey on School of Business and Computer Studies (SBCS) students at St. Dominic College of Asia. The statistical treatments used in the study were frequency and percentage to analyze the demographics of the respondents, weighted mean for the perception of the students in regard to the new method of learning, T-test to identify if there is significant difference in the performance based on gender, and two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to know if there is significant difference on the performance based between the courses. In this quantitative research, results are interpreted by the researchers to be comprehensible. Positive results are indicated by the findings showing that most of the students can adapt to the new system despite the technical difficulties encountered which are considered as the main hindrance. It was also highlighted that the students managed to attend their class early consistently, spend a lot of time on breaks, seek additional materials to learn from, and are highly recommended to set up a designated place for studying.

Keywords: Productivity; Online learning; Enhancement; Academic performance; School of Business and Computer Studies.

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Introduction

To which extent will online classes affect your focus as a student? The pandemic took the world by surprise. Everything has stopped. Our job suddenly moved into our home and school classes have been shifted to online learning due to the novel coronavirus. Online learning, also referred to as electronic learning (e-learning), is a modern way of education that serves as an alternative to traditional learning in the Philippines. It introduced developed school tasks that students must comply with that are different from the traditional learning system where use of technology and electronic gadgets are essential. This technological development provides an overwhelming growth in online learning in the Philippines and around the world, which contributes to the acceleration of education for all. The changing environment encourages schools, colleges and universities to seek additional platforms to continue to provide quality education. It used to cover a wide range of teaching practices that may in fact differ greatly in terms of learning outcomes and student access. Since students are learning at home, they have different kinds of commitments, responsibilities and areas in their daily life that need to be sustained. Students may have trouble dealing with numerous requirements besides studying at home.

This study will help to analyze the productivity level of the students on how they efficiently use their time on online learning in pursuing BS Business Administration, Bachelor in Multimedia Arts, BS Accountancy and BS Information Technology courses. The result of the study will be beneficial for students on how they can improve their work to become more productive in this time of online learning, professors that will guide and lead them to help students in enhancing their academic performance, and future researchers who would plan to do research for a similar topic. Specifically, this seeks answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents?
 - 1.1 Gender
 - 1.2 Course
2. How do the respondents perceive online learning as a tool of productivity in enhancing academic performance, in terms of:
 - 2.1 Attending online classes
 - 2.2 Class engagement
 - 2.3 Compliance with the requirements
 - 2.4 Commitment to increase productivity
3. How do the respondents perceive online learning as a tool of productivity in enhancing academic performance when grouped according to their profile variables?
4. Is there a significant difference in the perception of the respondents when grouped according to their profile variables?

Hypothesis

Ho. There is no significant relationship between the perception of the respondents between their gender and course.

Ha. There is a significant relationship between the perception of the respondents as between their gender and course.

Related Literature

Many colleges and universities are keen on the best ways to distribute course content for online learners as online education keeps growing. This study investigates how student engagement changes when courses are taken online. Several ordinary least squares regression models were used to examine the data, allowing for relevant institutional and student factors. Findings showed that both first year and senior students' participation in online courses was significantly correlated with their level of involvement. Students were more likely to use quantitative reasoning if they were enrolled in more online courses.

In contrast to their more conventional classroom colleagues, they were unable to participate in discussions with different individuals, student-faculty exchanges, and collaborative learning. Students who took more online courses also said they were less exposed to good teaching methods and that their interactions were of lower quality. An online setting may encourage some forms of involvement while discouraging others, based on the correlation between these engagement metrics and the proportion of online courses. These findings should be considered by institutions when creating the content for online courses, and they should also motivate faculty to think about promoting student participation in different delivery formats (Dumford & Miller, 2018).

Student engagement lowers feelings of loneliness, boosts motivation to learn, improves performance on online courses, and promotes student happiness. This survey-based research study examines student perception of various engagement strategies used in online courses based on Moore's (2013) interaction framework. This study also analyzed the effects of age, gender, and years of online learning experience differences on students' perception of engagement strategies. The results of the study have implications for online instructors, instructional designers, and administrators who wish to enhance engagement in online courses (Martin & Bolliger, 2018).

The Internet has made online learning possible, and many researchers and educators are interested in online learning to enhance and improve student learning outcomes while combating the reduction in resources, particularly in higher education. Researchers and educators consider the aspects that influence online learning success in comparison to traditional face-to-face instruction. By classifying and summarizing the results and difficulties of online learning into positive, negative, mixed, and null findings, this study investigates the evidence of its efficacy. Particular attention is paid to the meta-analyses on the effectiveness of online learning, the heterogeneous outcomes of student learning and the endogenous issue of learning environment choice. Taken as a whole, there is robust evidence to suggest online learning is generally at least as effective as the traditional format (Nguyen, 2015).

Similarly, Paul and Jefferson (2019) studied scores of 548 students, 401 traditional students and 147 online students, in an environmental science class, which was used to determine which instructional modality generated better student performance. Their overarching purpose was to determine which teaching method proved more effective over the 8-year period. There was no significant difference in the overall performance of online and in-person (F2F) learners by class rank, gender, or other factors. There was no significant gender difference in the performance of online and in-person learners based on the independent sample t-test. E-learning is the prevailing system in the present era for education, especially for young people's education, and motivates students to do their work without others' help. It is a system that provides time flexibility for students for their learning and the use of online learning gives them access to the global world for study purposes. E-learning also engages the students in the learning process (Salamat et al., 2018).

Shore (n.d.) mentioned in his article that an online class eliminates human connection and therefore student motivation, interaction, and educator's ability to adapt course materials and presentations is somehow lost. In contrast, Obana (2020) noted in his paper that the difficulties with online learning include technical problems, time management and distraction, maintaining motivation, understanding the requirements of the course, missing face-to-face interaction, adjusting to new technology, and future uncertainty. Both clearly stated that there are different challenges commonly encountered by students in their online learning (Belgica et al., 2020).

Likewise, most of the graduate students were ready for Open and Distance eLearning (ODeL). The attitude of the graduate students at ODeL was positive. Regarding the correlation of profile and readiness of students, there was a significant relationship between the level of education of the respondents with their self-direction and study habits, between the licensure examination passed and their study habits, and between years of teaching and their computer equipment abilities. While teachers and students, especially millennials, had a more positive outlook on online education, experienced teachers were also willing to adapt to the changing environment in education. Thus, graduate students or grade schoolteachers were found to be ready for online learning (Ventayen & Orlanda, 2018).

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized quantitative research design in the study. Quantitative research evaluates the problem by generating numerical data that can be analyzed using statistical methods. A survey

questionnaire, comprised of Likert-scale questions, is used in collecting data deemed necessary for the study.

Sample

The respondents comprised of 50 students from St. Dominic College of Asia from academic years 2020 – 2021. The research locale of the study is within the area of St. Dominic College of Asia, which is in Emilio Aguinaldo Highway, Bacoor, Cavite. The respondents were surveyed via Google Forms in compliance with the safety precautions of the government. The participants of the study are students from St. Dominic College of Asia who are taking a degree online within the School of Business and Computer Studies Department.

The researchers used a simple random sampling in the study, where every item in the population has an even chance and likelihood of being selected. The data collection was based on the survey questionnaire distributed to the respondents online and this serves as the primary research instrument in order for the study to accumulate data and to achieve its objectives, which is to know the level of productivity of the respondents on an online learning basis and for the further process, as researchers, were able to provide information on how they can improve their academic performance.

Instruments

The researchers used a survey questionnaire which consisted of two parts. The first part contained the demographic information of the respondents, while the second part outlined Likert-scale questions which consists of 20 questions that are divided into four categories, according to attending online classes, class engagement, compliance with the requirements and commitment to increasing productivity. Through this survey questionnaire, the researchers can gather data for the respondents about online learning if it helps students' productivity in enhancing academic performance. The researchers will be able to give recommendations afterward that are necessary in improving the study habits of SBCS students. This will help us find information that is needed to answer the statements about the problem.

Data Collection and Analysis

The study used primary data that was collected by online survey distribution using Google Forms. The researchers made a survey questionnaire that serves as a tool to collect information from our respondents. Upon approval, an online survey was used as an instrument in conducting the study. The proponents approached different year levels who agreed to participate in the study to complete 50 respondents. After collecting all the data, the data was tabulated and tallied. The responses gathered were analyzed and measured into statistical, mathematical, or computational form. The results were presented in percentages, tables and/or in figures with relevant interpretation to be more comprehensive.

Quantitative analysis is used because it reflects a structured cause-and-effect relationship between the problem and factors. It focuses on the quantification of data which allows the generalization of the results obtained from a sample to a population of interest. This research is based on numeric figures or numbers wherein the objective is to develop and employ mathematical models, theories, or hypothesis. It is conclusive in its purpose as it tries to quantify the problem and understand how prevalent it is by looking for projectable results for a larger population.

The researchers collected information from the students using sampling methods and by sending out online questionnaires. The results of which are depicted in the form of numbers. After careful understanding, the results achieved from this research method are logical, statistical, and unbiased.

The study adopted statistical treatment of data through percentage and frequency methods to determine the profile of the respondents according to course and gender. A weighted mean was used to identify the perception level of respondents in online learning. The two sample T-Test with unequal variance was applied to the main variables of the study, while a two-factor analysis of variance was utilized to test the significant differences of a scaled dependent variable to another variable with three categories.

The Likert scale in Table 1 is also used to measure the perception of the respondents regarding attending online classes, class engagement, compliance with the requirements, and commitment to increase productivity, and it is as follows:

Table 1. Likert scale perception of the respondents

Variables	Range in Mean Value	Description	Interpretation
Attending Online Classes	1.00-1.75	Strongly Disagree	Very Low Attentiveness
	1.76-2.50	Disagree	Low Attentiveness
	2.51-3.25	Agree	High Attentiveness
	3.26-4.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Attentiveness
Class Engagement	1.00-1.75	Strongly Disagree	Very Low Engagement
	1.76-2.50	Disagree	Low Engagement
	2.51-3.25	Agree	High Engagement
	3.26-4.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Engagement
Compliance with the Requirements	1.00-1.75	Strongly Disagree	Very Low Compliance
	1.76-2.50	Disagree	Low Compliance
	2.51-3.25	Agree	High Compliance
	3.26-4.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Compliance
Commitment to Increase Productivity	1.00-1.75	Strongly Disagree	Very Low Commitment
	1.76-2.50	Disagree	Low Commitment
	2.51-3.25	Agree	High Commitment
	3.26-4.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Commitment

Results and Discussion

Table 2. Profile of the respondents (n=50)

Category	Variables	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	26	52%
	Female	24	48%
Course	Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA)	15	30%
	Bachelor of Multimedia Arts (BMMA)	15	30%
	Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA)	8	16%
	Bachelor of Science in Information Technology (BSIT)	12	24%

Table 2 shows the profile of the respondents. It shows that out of 50 respondents, 26 or 52% of them are males, while 24 or 48% are females. It is also revealed that most respondents came from the BS Business Administration and Bachelor in Multimedia Arts, followed by the students from BS Information Technology and BS Accountancy.

Table 3. Perception of the Respondents on Online Learning

Factors	Mean	Interpretation
Attending online classes	2.83	High Attentiveness Level
Class engagement	2.98	High Engagement Level
Complying with the requirements	2.90	High Compliance Level
Commitment to increase productivity	2.88	High Commitment Level

Table 2 shows how the respondents perceived online learning in terms of attending online classes, class engagement, complying with the requirements, and commitment to increase productivity. Results showed SBCS students at St. Dominic College of Asia had a positive response. Under the variable attending online classes, researchers obtained a mean value of 2.83, which means that the respondents are highly attentive in online classes. The result revealed that most of the SBCS students make sure to attend online class on time. They can also keep up with their online classes with their updated gadgets, although it is also revealed that most of them encountered technical difficulties which may affect their productivity and performance as a student. Moreover, some of the respondents opened other software and applications during online classes because they want to entertain themselves. However, because students are studying at home, some of them do other tasks during online classes.

The class engagement of the respondents during online class showed a mean value of 2.98, which indicates that their level of engagement is high. The result showed that most of the respondents listen to the discussion and take note of the lecture during online classes. They review their notes to fully understand the subject after online class, study in advance for upcoming subjects, and actively participate in recitations as well as ask questions if the lesson seems unclear, or they do not understand. Additionally, the respondents watch recorded meetings and other tutorial videos related to the lecture to help them understand the lessons. It indicates that the respondents are highly engaged in discussions despite being online.

In terms of complying with the requirements, researchers obtained a mean value of 2.90, which indicates that the respondents are highly compliant during online learning. They plan their own study schedule to maximize their time and avoid procrastination and cramming when doing tasks. They also make sure to take breaks in between their studies. Other than that, respondents are found to be resourceful. They look for additional eligible resources other than the files or documents given by their professors.

Under commitment to increase productivity, a mean value of 2.88 was obtained and this indicates that the respondents have a high commitment to online learning. This factor involves some strategies for online learning, such as setting up designated study spaces, avoiding distractions, use of productivity applications and having enough sleep. The results showed that SBCS students are using these strategies to increase their productivity during online classes and are still committed to focusing on their course, whether it is face-to-face or virtual classes. This proved that despite the challenges faced, students learn the best ways to cope and pursue their dreams by adapting to their environment.

Likewise, the analysis that was made by Mobo and Sabado (2019) provided a definitive and elaborate study based on the results of the data gathered, wherein most of the respondents think that e-learning education is very good in terms of giving the students time to be flexible, allowing them to study and do other chores or even work.

Table 4. Perception of the Respondents on Online Learning when Grouped by Gender

Factors	Gender	Mean	Interpretation
Attending Online Classes	Male	2.94	High Attentiveness Level
	Female	2.71	High Attentiveness Level
Class Engagement	Male	2.92	High Engagement Level
	Female	3.04	High Engagement Level
Compliance with the Requirements	Male	2.92	High Compliance Level
	Female	2.88	High Compliance Level
Commitment to Increase Productivity	Male	2.99	High Commitment Level
	Female	2.76	High Commitment Level

Table 4 reveals the perception of the respondents on online learning when grouped by gender. As shown in the table above, male respondents gained a mean score of 2.94, which indicates a high attentiveness level; while female respondents gained a mean score of 2.71, which suggests a high attentiveness level. It implies that both male and female respondents are attentive in class.

Male respondents gained a mean score of 2.92, which indicates high engagement level; while female respondents gained a mean score of 3.04, which suggests high engagement level. It implies that both male and female respondents have the same level of class engagement.

Male respondents gained a mean score of 2.92, which indicates high compliance level; while female respondents gained a mean score of 2.88, which suggests high compliance level. It implies that both male and female respondents have the same level of compliance during online learning.

Male respondents gained a mean score of 2.99, which indicates high commitment level; while female respondents gained a mean score of 2.76, which suggests high commitment level. It implies that both male and female respondents have the same level of commitment to increase productivity.

Table 5. Perception of the Respondents on Online Learning when Grouped by Courses in School of Business and Computer Studies (SBCS)

Factors	Gender	Mean	Interpretation
Attending Online Classes	BSBA	3.16	High Attentiveness Level
	BMMA	2.44	Low Attentiveness Level
	BSA	2.90	High Attentiveness Level
	BSIT	2.50	Low Attentiveness Level
Class Engagement	BSBA	3.16	High Engagement Level
	BMMA	3.04	High Engagement Level
	BSA	3.08	High Engagement Level
	BSIT	2.53	High Engagement Level
Compliance with the Requirements	BSBA	3.17	High Compliance Level
	BMMA	2.76	High Compliance Level
	BSA	2.93	High Compliance Level
	BSIT	2.67	High Compliance Level
Commitment to Increase Productivity	BSBA	3.25	High Commitment Level
	BMMA	2.69	High Commitment Level
	BSA	3.18	High Commitment Level
	BSIT	2.53	High Commitment Level

Table 5 determines the perception of the respondents on online learning when grouped by courses in School of Business and Computer Studies (SBCS). In terms of attending online classes, BSBA respondents gained a mean score of 3.16, followed by BSA with 2.90, BSIT with 2.50, and BMMA with 2.44. It implies that BSBA and BSA students are more attentive than BMMA and BSIT students, considering their high attentiveness level. In terms of class engagement, BSBA respondents gained a mean score of 3.16, BSA with 3.08, BMMA with 3.04, and BSIT with 2.53. All programs indicated a high engagement level, which implies the same level of class engagement.

In terms of compliance with the requirements, BSBA respondents gained a mean score of 3.17, followed by BSA with 2.93, BMMA with 2.76, and BSIT with 2.67, suggesting a high compliance level for all programs. In terms of commitment to increase productivity, BSBA respondents gained a mean score of 3.25, followed by BSA with 3.18, BMMA with 2.69, and BSIT with 2.53, which suggests a high commitment level for all programs.

Table 6. Significant Differences on the Perception of the Respondents when grouped by Gender

Factors	Critical value	Computed t value	Decision
Attending online classes	2.011	1.42	Accept
Class engagement		0.75	Accept
Compliance with the requirements		0.21	Accept
Commitment to increase productivity		1.23	Accept

Table 6 shows the results of the t-test, a type of inferential statistic that is often used in hypothesis testing to determine whether a process or treatment influences the population of interest, or whether two groups are different from one another. It was done to determine if there is a significant difference in the productivity of the School of Business and Computer Studies students when grouped according to gender.

The data gathered and calculated showed a result of a computed t-value of 1.42, which is lower than the critical value of 2.011. This denotes that the null hypothesis should be accepted and that there is no significant difference as to the BSA students' manifestation of attending online classes. Since the computed t-value of 0.75 is lower than the critical value of 2.011, the null hypothesis is accepted. The difference between means was not enough to overcome the variation within the groups under class engagement. Therefore, there is no significant difference between genders.

In complying with the required attribute, the computed t value is 0.21, which is lower than the critical value of 2.011. The study failed to reject the null hypothesis and there was no significant difference in the performance of the students in terms of passing the tasks assigned between males and females. In commitment to increase productivity, the computed t value is 1.23, which is lower than the critical value of 2.011. Hence, the null hypothesis should be accepted and there is no significant difference between males and females when it comes to their techniques. The test showed that there is no significant difference when it comes to the attributes given. Both gender groups are attentive, engaged, compliant, and committed in the school.

Table 7. Significant Differences on the Perception of the Respondents when grouped according to Courses in SBCS

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-Value	F-crit
Sample	0.304375	3	0.101458	0.536	0.659	2.748
Columns	4.021375	3	1.340458	7.078	0.000	2.748
Interaction	1.114125	9	0.123792	0.654	0.747	2.030
Within	12.12	64	0.189375			
Total	17.55988	79				

Legend: $F > F\text{-crit}$ = significant difference; $F < F\text{-crit}$ = no significant difference; $P\text{-value} < \alpha$ = reject null hypothesis (H_0); $P\text{-value} > \alpha$ = accept null hypothesis (H_0); SS = Sum of Squares; df = degree of freedom; MS = mean of squares

The F-statistics in the sample is 0.536, which is less than the critical value of 2.748. Therefore, the proponents accept the null hypothesis that the means of the observations for attending online classes, class engagement, complying with the requirements, and commitment to productivity are the same, not in favor of the alternative hypothesis that they are different. The p-value is greater than the alpha 0.05, which is another evidence to accept the null hypothesis.

There is a high F-statistic which is way bigger than the critical value. The F-statistics are 7.078, while the critical value is only 2.748. Therefore, the proponents rejected the null hypothesis that the means of observation by the columns are the same in favor of the alternative hypothesis, meaning that there is a significant difference between the four of them. Moreover, the p-value is 0, so it is another evidence that the proponents should reject the null hypothesis.

Finally, in the interaction, the F-statistics are 0.654, which is less than the F-critical value of 2.030. Therefore, the proponents must accept the null hypothesis that there is no interaction between the factors, not in favor of the alternative hypothesis that there is an interaction. It is also clear that the P-value is greater than the alpha value of 0.05. It says that the course of the students is independent of their performance. On the other hand, it says that the performance of the students is independent of their course.

Online learning is an educational system that has become modernized here in the Philippines. This research aims to find out how the respondents perceive online learning as a tool of productivity in enhancing their academic performance in attending online classes, class engagement, complying with the requirements, and commitment to increasing productivity. Based on the results, the students of the SBCS department provide a positive result on different aspects that help them enhance their productivity in online learning. Results show a high level of attentiveness, engagement, compliance, and commitment. Therefore, even in online learning, students can still be productive despite the challenges and difficulties.

The attentiveness of both male students and female students has proven to be at the same level. In terms of online class engagement, compliance, and commitment to increasing productivity, both male and female students have proven to be at the same level of perception. The perception of online learning for different courses revealed that attending online classes, learning engagement, compliance, and commitment to increasing productivity are relatively close to one another at the same high level.

In the perception of respondents, when grouped according to their courses, the attentiveness level of BSBA and BSA students is higher than BMMA and BSIT students. In terms of class engagement, complying with the requirements, and commitment to increasing productivity, the four courses have proven to be at the same level of perception.

In using the T-test, the perception of both male and female students towards online learning attributes, which are attending online classes, class engagement, compliance, and commitment, is proven to have no significant difference. Both male and female students have the same level of the said online learning attributes.

In using ANOVA, the perception of students revealed that the means of observations for attending online classes, class engagement, complying with the requirements and commitment to increase productivity are the same increasing. There is no significant difference between the attributes. Most of the SBCS students are attentive, engaged, compliant, and committed. In the column part which includes the SBCS courses, there is a significant difference between the four groups in the results. This revealed that even though they try their best to be dynamic, BMMA and BSIT students find traditional classes more effective than online classes. Lastly, in the interaction part, there is no significant difference between the course and the performance of the students. The course is independent of the performance of the students, and it is biased to judge the performance of the students by their course.

The objectives of this study are to find out the impact of changes towards productivity and enhancement of students on online learning. The study showed that the adjustment to the new method is challenged by distraction and insufficient technology of the students. It also showed that many of the students were able to use the advantage of the internet to find more study materials to cope with missed lessons.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Researchers discovered the routine, participation, challenges, and strategies of SBCS students when it comes to an online class. These also include how they manage their time and pass the tasks assigned. Based on the results, students who are engaged in an online class have proven to be productive. Despite challenges in online learning, students strive to overcome and find things to help them adapt to this learning style.

The proponents, therefore, conclude that despite the heavy adjustments of the education system during the pandemic, the SBCS students still do their best to learn and survive by trying to adapt to the circumstances. SBCS students stay focused on the betterment of themselves and find ways to resolve such problems.

During online classes, although they do other things, they want to be more productive and maximize the things they can do in a short amount of time. These consist of their responsibility as a student and a family member. Moreover, it takes a lot of sacrifices and consequences, especially because most of them have difficulties to encounter, but because of their dreams, they still try to continue, given that it will never be easy. They need to maintain their skills and meet their expectations. Also, it is hard to live in the virtual world. The essence are the opportunities, friendship, and skills that are enhanced. Their character remains constant regardless of the situation.

For the enhancement of academic performance, most SBCS students' habit is to attend their classes early to be more productive, so it is advised to make sure they are not late to avoid catching up with the discussions and preserve the time allotted for other things. In compliance with the requirements, most of the respondents give themselves a break between studying, which is necessary to take short naps or breaks for better performance. Students who want to do good in school should prioritize their health above all.

In addition, another tip is that using additional learning materials such as books, PDFs, and sample test banks is a must. The Internet itself and the activities that are given are usually not enough when taking different courses. To survive, you need to be hardworking, patient, and possess the need to learn. When it comes to strategy, results showed that most SBCS students set up a designated space for studying. It shows that for better concentration, especially when the major subjects are composed of solving and analysis, it is essential that the student needs to be in a peaceful environment to be more focused.

Straightaway, most students still prefer face-to-face classes to online classes, because even if they survive this kind of method, the time for discussion in traditional classes is longer, the skills are more enhanced, demonstrations are guided by instructors with live, questions are raised and dealt with immediately, and learning experience is more reliable. Furthermore, most SBCS students are more motivated to study when it is face-to-face classes, regardless of the positive results. Several students under the department stopped enrolling this academic year when the proponents tried to approach them with the questionnaires. They believe that it is not that effective because they want more quality experience to learn. Once the situation of a pandemic gets better, it is advisable to bring back the old way of teaching and to not depend on the power of technology itself.

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